

CODEN [USA]: IAJ PBB

ISSN: 2349-7750

**INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF
PHARMACEUTICAL SCIENCES**Available online at: <http://www.iajps.com>

Research Article

**VAGINAL LACTOBACILLI PROFILE IN PREGNANT WOMEN
WITH NORMAL AND ABNORMAL FLORA**¹Dr.Sila Aman, ²Dr.Iqra Zaheen¹Rawalpindi Medical College, ²Punjab Medical College Faisalabad.

Article Received: April 2019

Accepted: May 2019

Published: June 2019

Abstract:

Background & objectives: Lactobacilli species that are better adapted to vaginal environment of women may colonize better and offer protection against vaginal pathogenic bacteria. This study deals with the distribution of common Lactobacillus species which were investigated in pregnant women.

Methods: Sixty seven pregnant women were included in the study and vaginal samples were collected for Gram staining. Based on Nugent's score the subjects were classified as normal, intermediate flora and bacterial vaginosis (BV). In this study we also collected vaginal samples to identify Lactobacillus spp. by multiplex polymerase chain reaction (PCR) profiling of 16S rDNA amplification method.

Results: The most predominant Lactobacillus spp. found in pregnant women (normal flora) was Lactobacillus crispatus (100%), subsequently L. iners (77%), L. jensenii (74%) and L. helveticus (60%). L. iners was found to be common across all groups in women with all three flora, L. crispatus, a significant decrease was presented by L. jensenii and L. helveticus as the vaginal flora changed to intermediate and BV. Except L. iners, other species of lactobacilli prevalence was less frequent in women with BV. Species such as L. rhamnosus, L. fermentum, L. paracasei and L. casei were not detected in any vaginal sample.

Interpretation & conclusions: Predominant species in women with normal flora were L. crispatus, L. jensenii and L. helveticus. L. crispatus alone or in combination with L. jensenii and L. helveticus could be evaluated for probiotic properties to prevent and treat BV.

Corresponding author:

Dr. Sila Aman,
Rawalpindi Medical College.

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Please cite this article in press Sila Aman et al., *Vaginal Lactobacilli Profile in Pregnant Women with Normal and Abnormal Flora.*, Indo Am. J. P. Sci, 2019; 06(06).

INTRODUCTION:

The beneficial microbiota such as *Lactobacillus* spp. in vaginal ecosystem is thought to have been adapted and coevolved by mutualistic association with its human host¹. It is essential to explore the *Lactobacillus* diversity of vagina in health and disease and to understand whether changes in the individual vaginal *Lactobacillus* spp. can be correlated with changes in vaginal infections². Bacterial vaginosis (BV) is a common vaginal infection caused by imbalance of indigenous microbiota^{3,4}. Disturbance in the vaginal flora with overgrowth of bacteria that are present in the vagina in small numbers such as *Gardnerella vaginalis*, *Prevotella*, *Mobiluncus*, *Peptostreptococcus* and decrease in the number of *Lactobacillus* spp. often associated with high pH and clue cells is generally described as BV^{5,6}. BV is known to increase predisposition to sexually transmitted diseases, including gonorrhoea, chlamydia, syphilis, trichomoniasis, human immunodeficiency virus and human papilloma virus^{7,8}. In pregnancy, BV increases the risk of post-abortion sepsis, early miscarriage, recurrent abortion, late miscarriage, preterm premature rupture of membranes, spontaneous preterm labour and histologic chorioamnionitis⁹⁻¹¹.

Therapy of BV involves oral or local administration of metronidazole or intravaginal clindamycin and varies in efficacy³. The long-term cure rate is low, and BV recurs in up to 40 per cent of women within three months after initiation of antibiotic therapy and in up to 50 per cent of women after three months¹². There are several side-effects and disadvantages associated with these therapies, including superinfections by pathogenic microorganisms and disturbance of gut flora when treated by oral supplementation¹³. Moreover, vaginal opportunistic pathogens, particularly *G. vaginalis* and anaerobic bacteria show increasing drug resistance. In this context, *Lactobacillus* spp. administered orally or locally may be an effective alternative therapy which would re-establish the indigenous *Lactobacillus* and prevent BV as well as associated complications².

In humans, about 120 *Lactobacillus* species have been identified and more than 20 species have been found in the vagina¹⁴. Based on the previous molecular-based vaginal microbiome studies, three or four species (mainly *Lactobacillus crispatus*, *Lactobacillus iners*, *Lactobacillus jensenii* and *Lactobacillus gasseri*) normally predominate¹⁴⁻¹⁶. Colonization by lactobacilli ensures low pH in the genital tract (pH 4.5), which protects against colonization by other microbes⁷. *Lactobacillus*

species also protect vaginal health by producing antimicrobial compounds such as hydrogen peroxide and bacteriocins¹⁷. This study was undertaken to identify and study the vaginal lactobacilli profile of pregnant women with normal, disturbed (intermediate flora) and BV flora.

MATERIAL & METHODS:

Pregnant women were selected from Gyn and Obs Department of Holy Family Hospital Rawalpindi. Sixty seven women were selected for the study after obtaining written informed consent.

The sample size was calculated with preliminary data on vaginal lactobacilli in normal women; based on which, 18 per group were found to be sufficient to detect significance at 5 per cent between groups with 80 per cent power. At the first study visit, weight, age, height and blood sample (0.2 ml) for haemoglobin levels were collected. Gestational age was calculated based on the last menstrual period, and birth weight was recorded. Vaginal samples (vaginal exudates of lateral wall) were collected for the identification of *Lactobacillus* spp. from all the 67 pregnant women. The women were classified into BV, intermediate and normal according to the Nugent score (NS) criteria based on vaginal smear Gram staining scores¹⁸ using Microscope (Olympus B202, Japan). NS of 1-3 is considered normal vaginal flora or normal microbiota (BV negative), NS of 4-6 is considered as intermediate vaginal flora or intermediate microbiota, and 7-10 is considered as BV positive¹⁸. All women diagnosed with BV were treated with local antibiotic (Clindamycin 2% vaginal cream) for one week as per the WHO guidelines¹⁹. The first swab was used to prepare a smear on a glass slide for the purpose of grading¹⁸. The second swab was transferred to a sterile phosphate buffer saline (PBS) tube for DNA extraction.

DNA Extraction from vaginal swabs and Lactobacilli identification by Multiplex PCR: DNA extraction from vaginal swab samples was carried out as described by Kumar *et al*²⁰. The polymerase chain reaction (AESTAC, Japan) was carried out for isolated DNA samples. Each sample was initially identified to the genus level by amplification with genus-specific primers, [forward primer (F) CTCAAACACTAAACAAAGTTTC-F and reverse primer (R), CTTGTACACACCGCCCGTTCA-R] [250 base pairs (bp) product size]. PCR programme included initial denaturation at 94°C for five minutes, followed by 30 cycles of denaturation at 94°C for 30 sec, annealing at 56°C and extension at 72°C for five minutes. Amplified product was identified on Low EEO agarose gel using Geldoc (Syngene, UK).

Samples positive for *Lactobacillus* genus were subjected to species identification using species-specific primers 21-23 (Table I). Multiplex PCR was used for the identification of 17 *Lactobacillus* spp. as given in Table I. Species was identified on Low EEO agarose gel using Geldoc based on product size and 1 kb ladder DNA. For each sample, PCR reaction was carried out independently in duplicates.

Cultivation of lactobacilli bacteria from vaginal swabs in MRS broth:

The vaginal swabs were vortexed in 1 ml sterile PBS (pH 7.4) to prepare bacterial suspensions and 100 µl of sample was inoculated in freshly prepared sterile MRS broth (BD Difco™, USA). After incubation for

48 h under anaerobic condition (anaerobic workstation, N₂ 80%, CO₂ 10%, H₂ 10%) at 37°C, samples positive for growth were used for DNA extraction. DNA extraction and PCR procedures followed were similar to those mentioned above.

Statistical analysis:

ANOVA was performed to compare means of NS and pH in women with normal, intermediate and BV flora and Chi-square was used to compare proportions between groups using SPSS version 22.0 software (SPSS, Chicago, IL, USA). Heat map was created using R-programme software package (G-PLOT HEATMAP 2) to depict the frequency of the lactobacilli species.

Table I. Sequences of polymerase chain reaction primers used for the identification of lactobacilli by multiplex polymerase chain reaction

Multiplex PCR group	Species name	Primer sequence (5'-3')	Product size (bp)
1	<i>Lactobacillus criptatus</i>	AGGATATGGAGAGCAGGAA T-F	522
		CAACTATCTCTTACTGCC -R	
	<i>L. jensenii</i>	AAGAAGGCACTGAGTACGG A-F	700
		CCTTCCCTCACGGTACTG-R	
	<i>L. gasseri</i>	AGCGACCGAGAAGAGAGAG A-F	360
		TGCTATCGCTTCAAGTGCTT- R	
2	<i>L. delbrueckii</i>	ACAGATGGATGGAGAGCAG A-F	450

		CCTCTTCGCTCGCCGCTACT-R	
	<i>L. acidophilus</i>	TGCAAAGTGGTAGCGTAAGC-F	210
		AAGAAGGCACTGAGTACGGA-R	
3	<i>L. iners</i>	GTCTGCCTTGAAGATCGG-F	158
		ACAGTTGATAGGCATCATC-R	
	<i>L. johnsonii</i>	TCGAGCGAGCTTGCCTAGATGA-F	527
		TCCGGACAACGCTTGCCACC-R	
	<i>L. helveticus</i>	GCAGCAGAACCAGCAGATT-T-F	219
		GCATCATTGCCTTGTAAGC-R	
4	<i>L. reuteri</i>	CAGACAATCTTTGATTGTTT-AG-F	303
		GCTTGTTGGTTTGGGCTCTT-C-R	
	<i>L. fermentum</i>	ACTAACTGACTGATCTACGA-F	192
		TTCACTGCTCAAGTAATCATC-R	
	<i>L. vaginalis</i>	GCCTAACCATTTGGAGGG-F	550
		CGATGTGTAGGTTTCCG-R	
5	<i>L. bravis</i>	CTTCTGGATGATCCCGCGGC-G-F	369
		ACCGCCTGCGCTCGCTTTAC-R	
	<i>L. salivarius</i>	AATCGCTAAACTCATAACCT-F	411
		CACTCTCTTTGGCTAATCTT-R	
	<i>L. plantarum</i>	ATTCATAGTCTAGTTGGAGG-T-F	248
		CCTGAACTGAGAGAATTTGA-R	
6	<i>L. paracasei</i>	GGCCAGCTATGTATCACTG	312

		A-F	
		CTAGCGGGTGCGACTTTGTT -R	
	<i>L. casei</i>	TGCACTGAGTTCGACTTAA- F	500
		CCCCTGCTGCCTCCCGTAG GAGT-R	
	<i>L. rhamnosus</i>	GCGATGCGAATTTCTATTAT T-F	113
		CTAGCGGGTGCGACTTTGTT -R	

Table II. Demographic and clinical characteristics of pregnant women and neonates						
Characteristics		Overall (n=67)	Normal (n=27)	Intermediate(n=21)	BV positive (n=19)	P
Age (yr)		22.24±2.17	22.50±2.21	22.05±2.42	22.11±1.84	0.742
Height (cm)		152.43±5.00	151.91±4.46	154.23±5.68	150.99±4.42	0.097
Weight (kg)		52.76±8.06	51.60±7.20	53.45±8.62	53.58±8.77	0.649
BMI (kg/m ²)		22.7±2.7	22.5±3.7	21.8±2.1	23.9±3.7	0.444
Gestational age at recruitment (wk)		23.20±5.06	23.88±6.07	23.16±4.46	22.33±4.21	0.627
pH		5.02±0.47	4.77±0.38	5.09±0.29	5.31±0.57	0.001
Nugent's score		4.47±2.37	2.31±0.74	4.18±0.50	7.94±0.64	0.001
Amsel's criteria (%)		40.9 (27)	7.7 (2)	45.5 (10)	83.3 (15)	0.001
Gestational age at delivery (wk)		38.84±1.43	38.43±1.59	39.05±1.32	39.11±1.28	0.232
Birth weight (kg)		2.64±0.50	2.68±0.54	2.61±0.45	2.60±0.52	0.842
Low birth weight (%)		24.2 (15)	26.1 (6)	28.6 (6)	16.7 (3)	0.664
Pre-term deliveries		5.9 (5)	11.1 (3)	4.7 (1)	5.2 (1)	0.540

Values mean±SD. BMI, body mass index; BV, bacterial vaginosis; SD, standard deviation

Fig. 1. Heatmap shows proportions of microbial species found in the vaginal bacterial communities of 67 pregnant women. As the colour key indicates, light green colour represents the absence of the organisms, and the darker coloured tiles indicate the presence of percentage of that particular organism. *Lactobacillus crispatus* was the dominant flora in the normal and intermediate group and *L. iners* was the more frequent organism in the positive group. Nugent's score and pH bars are shown on the right side of the Figure. The Nugent's score increased with increasing Ph

Fig. 2. Percentage of the most frequent vaginal *Lactobacillus* spp. in women with normal, intermediate and bacterial vaginosis flora as determined by multiplex polymerase chain reaction profile.

RESULTS & DISCUSSION:

Mean age, weight, height, body mass index and haemoglobin concentration were similar in women with normal, intermediate and BV flora. Of the 67 pregnant women, 15 had low birth weight babies (birth weight <2.5 kg) and five had preterm deliveries (gestational age at delivery <37 week) (Table II). The mean birth weight and gestational age at delivery were comparable between groups. Of the 67 pregnant women, 27 had normal vaginal flora, 21 had intermediate flora and 19 had BV. The vaginal pH and NS means were significantly ($P < 0.001$) higher in women with BV compared to normal.

Only 13 of the 17 lactobacilli species were detected by multiplex PCR. Heatmap (Fig. 1) shows distribution of lactobacilli species in pregnant women *L. jensenii*, *L. vaginalis* and *L. helveticus*. Species such as *L. rhamnosus*, *L. fermentum*, *L. paracasei* and *L. casei* were not detected by multiplex PCR.

The proportion of pregnant women with *Lactobacillus* spp. in normal, intermediate and BV flora are shown in Fig. 2. *L. crispatus* (100%) was the most predominant *Lactobacillus* spp. present in pregnant women with normal flora, followed by *L.*

iners (77%), *L. jensenii* (74%) and *L. helveticus* (60%) (Fig. 2). Significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher proportion of women with normal flora had *L. crispatus* compared to women with intermediate flora and BV. Similarly, *L. jensenii* and *L. helveticus* were significantly ($P < 0.05$) higher in women with normal flora compared to women with BV (Fig. 2). *L. iners* was commonly present across groups in women with normal, intermediate or BV flora. Except *L. iners*, other species of lactobacilli were less frequently prevalent in women with BV.

Four of 27 pregnant women with normal flora had a combination of *L. crispatus*, *L. jensenii*, *L. helveticus* and *L. acidophilus* and this combination was not found in women with intermediate or BV flora. In contrast, *L. iners*, *L. gasseri*, *L. vaginalis* and *L. salivarius* combination were found in three women with intermediate and two with BV flora; interestingly, this combination was not found in normal group. Combination of *L. iners*, *L. gasseri* and *L. vaginalis* was found in both intermediate and BV groups, but not in normal flora. However, a combination of *L. iners* along with *L. crispatus*, *L. jensenii*, *L. helveticus* and *L. reuteri* was found in three of 27 women with normal flora, a similar combination was observed less frequently in women

with intermediate and BV microbiota.

By culture-dependant method, 12 lactobacilli spp. (*L. crispatus*, *L. jensenii*, *L. gasseri*, *L. iners*, *L. helveticus*, *L. vaginalis*, *L. bravis*, *L. johnsoni*, *L. acidophilus*, *L. reuteri*, *L. paracasei* and *L. salivarius*) could be identified from women with normal flora and intermediate flora while, none of the lactobacilli spp. could be isolated from vaginal samples of women with BV flora. *Lactobacillus delbrueckii*, which could be detected by multiplex PCR, could not be isolated by culture-dependent method from any vaginal samples. In culture-dependent method *L. iners*, *L. jensenii* and *L. crispatus* were detected only in 33, 39 and 61 per cent compared to 78.3, 70.2 and 91.8 per cent by multiplex PCR method. *L. gasseri* (50%) and *L. reuteri* (28%) isolation rates in MRS broth, however, were similar to multiplex PCR (*L. gasseri*, 51%; *L. reuteri*, 22%). *L. paracasei* on the other hand, which was not detected by multiplex PCR was isolated from eight per cent of pregnant women.

Our findings showed that *L. crispatus*, *L. iners*, *L. gasseri*, *L. jensenii* and *L. vaginalis* dominated the vaginal microbiota of Pakistani women, which was similar to those found in European and Brazilian women^{2,22}. A similar *Lactobacillus* spp. profile in vagina has been reported from South Africa²⁴. In our study, *L. helveticus* was identified more commonly in Pakistani women with normal flora which was less frequent in several other studies^{25,26}.

An association between the presence of *L. crispatus* and absence of BV has been shown²⁷. Association of *L. crispatus* has been observed with stability of the vaginal microbiota²⁸. Several clinical trials have been performed to investigate the efficacy of specific strains of *L. rhamnosus*, *L. fermentum* and *L. reuteri* administered either orally or intravaginally in treating BV or urogenital infections²⁷. *L. fermentum* and *L. rhamnosus* probiotic strains have been used with poor results in preventing BV²⁶. Their uncommon presence in the vagina as observed in the current study and uncertain role in vaginal health may be the reason for the failure of efficacy with *L. fermentum* and *L. rhamnosus*.

The presence of *L. gasseri*, *L. vaginalis* and *L. iners* in women with intermediate and BV flora as observed in the current study could be due to their poorer colonization resistance to pathogens or inadequate production of antimicrobial substances, thereby allowing overgrowth of other pathogenic bacteria. Longitudinal studies in pregnant women have also shown that women harbouring *Lactobacillus* spp.,

particularly *L. gasseri* and *L. iners*, are more susceptible to BV compared to those colonized by *L. crispatus*^{26,28}. Similar findings were observed in the present study, but *L. vaginalis* was also found to be commonly associated with intermediate and BV flora.

There are many commercially available probiotic strains for BV treatment. Most of the strains (*L. acidophilus*, *L. casei*, *L. plantarum*, *L. lactis*, *L. jensenii* and *Bifidobacterium bifidum*, *Bifidobacterium infantis*, etc.) that are available on the market are not frequently found in women with normal vaginal flora²⁶. From our observations, it may be speculated that *L. iners*, *L. gasseri* and *L. vaginalis* may become a dominant part of the vaginal microbiota when the microbiota is in a transitional stage from normal to abnormal vaginal flora. Hence, *L. crispatus* individually or in combination with *L. jensenii*, *L. helveticus* and *L. acidophilus*, may be evaluated for probiotic potential to combat BV.

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